

TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS WITH THE HELP OF MULTIMEDIA IN ENHANCED LESSONS

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***Abstract.** Learning takes place at different levels and in different modes. At its most basic, multimedia can enable the recognition of words, terms, and their contextual meaning. These are the simple vocabulary trainers for foreign languages or technical terms. They are the multimedia equivalent of multiple choice tests for the learning and testing of contextual meaning. This article describes teaching English to young learners with the help of multimedia in enhanced lessons.*

***Key words:** Multimedia, multimedia technologies, multimedia instruction, perception, learning styles.*

Multimedia is a form of communication that uses a combination of different content forms such as text, audio, images, animations, or video into a single interactive presentation, in contrast to traditional mass media, such as printed material or audio recordings, which features little to no interaction between users. Popular examples of multimedia include video podcasts, audio slideshows and animated videos. Multimedia also contains the principles and application of effective interactive communication such as the building blocks of software, hardware, and other technologies. Multimedia can be recorded for playback on computers, laptops, smartphones, and other electronic devices, either on demand or in real time (streaming). In the early years of multimedia, the term "rich media" was synonymous with interactive multimedia. Over time, hypermedia extensions brought multimedia to the World Wide Web.

In education, multimedia is used to produce computer-based training courses (popularly called CBTs) and reference books like encyclopedia and almanacs. A

CBT lets the user go through a series of presentations, text about a particular topic, and associated illustrations in various information formats. Learning theory in the past decade has expanded dramatically because of the introduction of multimedia. Several lines of research have evolved, e.g. cognitive load and multimedia learning. From multimedia learning theory, David Roberts has developed a large group lecture practice using PowerPoint and based on the use of full-slide images in conjunction with a reduction of visible text. The method has been applied and evaluated in 9 disciplines. In each experiment, students' engagement and active learning have been approximately 66% greater, than with the same material being delivered using bullet points, text, and speech, corroborating a range of theories presented by multimedia learning scholars like Sweller and Mayer. The idea of media convergence is also becoming a major factor in education, particularly higher education. Defined as separate technologies such as voice (and telephony features), data (and productivity applications), and video that now share resources and interact with each other, media convergence is rapidly changing the curriculum in universities all over the world. Higher education has been implementing the use of social media applications such as Twitter, YouTube, Facebook, etc. to increase student collaboration and develop new processes in how information can be conveyed to students.

Multimedia provides students with an alternate means of acquiring knowledge designed to enhance teaching and learning through various mediums and platforms. In the 1960s, technology began to expand into the classrooms through devices such as screens and telewriters. This technology allows students to learn at their own pace and gives teachers the ability to observe the individual needs of each student. The capacity for multimedia to be used in multi-disciplinary settings is structured around the idea of creating a hands-on learning environment through the use of technology. Lessons can be tailored to the subject matter as well as be personalized to the students' varying levels of knowledge on the topic. Learning content can be managed through activities that utilize and take advantage of multimedia platforms. This kind of usage of modern multimedia encourages interactive communication between students and teachers and opens feedback channels, introducing an active learning

process especially with the prevalence of new media and social media. Technology has impacted multimedia as it is largely associated with the use of computers or other electronic devices and digital media due to its capabilities concerning research, communication, problem-solving through simulations and feedback opportunities. The innovation of technology in education through the use of multimedia allows for diversification among classrooms to enhance the overall learning experience for students. With the spread and development of the English language around the world, multimedia has become an important way of communicating between different people and cultures. Multimedia Technology creates a platform where language can be taught. The traditional form of teaching English as a Second Language in classrooms have drastically changed with the prevalence of technology, making easier for students to obtain language learning skills. Multimedia motivates students to learn more languages through audio, visual and animation support. It also helps create English contexts since an important aspect of learning a language is developing their grammar, vocabulary and knowledge of pragmatics and genres. In addition, cultural connections in terms of forms, contexts, meanings and ideologies have to be constructed. By improving thought patterns, multimedia develops students' communicative competence by improving their capacity to understand the language. One of the studies, carried out by Izquierdo, Simard and Pulido, presented the correlation between "Multimedia Instruction and learners' second language" and its effects on learning behavior. Their findings based on Gardner's theory of the "socio-educational model of learner motivation and attitudes", the study shows that there is easier access to language learning materials as well as increased motivation with Multimedia Instruction along with the use of Computer-Assisted Language Learning. Learning takes place at different levels and in different modes. At its most basic, multimedia can enable the recognition of words, terms, and their contextual meaning. These are the simple vocabulary trainers for foreign languages or technical terms. They are the multimedia equivalent of multiple choice tests for the learning and testing of contextual meaning.

At the next level, perception begins to play a role as shapes and colors, graphic elements, and movement through space and/or time allows the user to ask questions about the contents of pictures or sequences of movement. Multimedia computing still offers many unexploited possibilities for this kind of learning, especially in the field of art history. Multimedia computing can also be used to pursue the didactical aim of furthering creativity: finding a suitable description of an art object, manipulating scanned pictures, rearranging the pictures in a digital exhibition, or simply grouping colors and shapes, all exercise visual learning and perception. Multimedia has been shown to be effective for learning: animations effectively stimulate learner interest and thus enhance the learning experience with augmented reality improving the students' cognitive skills by provided a platform to combine digital and physical parameters. Positive findings of these studies suggest that the use of multimedia as a form of blended-learning technique cater to the multiple learning styles and have been found to provide better outcomes than traditional lecture delivery. Research conducted into the learning styles of the students provided an explanation to why interactive multimedia may prove beneficial to their learning experience.

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